

Unlocking the Potential of Open Research Software in Acoustics

Nantes, 29-30 August 2024

Instructions and guidelines for acceleration of sharing research software

Maarten Hornikx

Department of the Built Environment

Guide to sharing your software

- Disclaimer: this presentation is not exhaustive, we are not software engineers 😊
- Please add information/suggestion to HackMD, such that we can improve it for all of us!
<https://tinyurl.com/Open-Acoustics>

SOFTWARE SUSTAINABILITY INSTITUTE

About News, blogs and events Programmes Training Resources Search

About us

The Software Sustainability Institute is the first organisation in the world that was dedicated to improving software in research. We help people build better and more sustainable software to enable world-class research.

Read more >

BETTER SOFTWARE BETTER RESEARCH

Contents

- Sharing software
- Licencing
- Collaborating
- Software citations
- Software in publications
- Visibility - Repositories/Platforms
- Software quality - Self (reviewing)
- Training

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3332807>

Sharing software, various alternatives

- Not sharing software behind research
- Sharing (e.g. via e-mail) upon request
- Sharing on (own) website
- Adding software to paper (as pseudocode in manuscript/supplementary material)
- Sharing via publicly accessible repositories (Institute repositories, version control platforms as GitLab and GitHub)
- Think about purpose of sharing: impact, collaboration, visibility, lasting accessibility
- In striving for [FAIR software](#) (similar to FAIR data), publicly accessible repositories are recommended

Sharing software, GitHub example

The screenshot shows the GitHub interface for the repository 'gpuRIR' by user 'DavidDiazGuerra'. The repository is public and has 10 watchers, 91 forks, and 470 stars. The main content area displays a list of commits, with the most recent one by 'DavidDiazGuerra' titled 'Fix memory leak #49' (commit hash f32633b, 6 months ago). Below the commit list are folders for 'examples', 'gpuRIR', 'src', and 'third_party/pybind11'. The right sidebar contains an 'About' section with the description 'Python library for Room Impulse Response (RIR) simulation with GPU acceleration' and several topic tags: 'python-library', 'gpu-acceleration', 'rir', 'acoustics', 'image-source-model', and 'room-impulse-responses'.

DavidDiazGuerra / gpuRIR

Code Issues 16 Pull requests 1 Actions Projects Security Insights

gpuRIR Public Watch 10 Fork 91 Star 470

master Go to file + Code

DavidDiazGuerra Fix memory leak #49 f32633b · 6 months ago

examples	Reduce the shared memory ...	2 years ago
gpuRIR	Implement source directivity ...	3 years ago
src	Fix memory leak #49	6 months ago
third_party/pybind11	GPU aceleration for simulate...	6 years ago

About

Python library for Room Impulse Response (RIR) simulation with GPU acceleration

python-library gpu-acceleration

rir acoustics

image-source-model

room-impulse-responses

Licencing

- A software license defines rules and conditions for people who want to use the software
- Many licences exist
- Find out what suits best at <https://choosealicense.com/appendix/>
- If your software builds on open source components from others, you are not free to chose

	Public domain & equivalents	Permissive license	Copyleft (protective license)	Noncommercial license	Proprietary license	Trade secret
Description	Grants all rights	Grants use rights, forbids almost nothing (allows proprietization, license compatibility)	Grants use rights, forbids proprietization	Grants rights for noncommercial use only. May not be combined with copyleft.	Traditional use of copyright ; no rights need be granted	No information made public
Software	PD, CC0	BSD , MIT , Apache	GPL , AGPL	JRL , AFPL	proprietary software , no public license	private, internal software
Other creative works	PD, CC0	CC BY	CC BY-SA , Free Art License	CC BY-NC , CC BY-NC-SA	Copyright , no public license	unpublished

Collaborating

Important aspects for collaboration

- Coding practices: code structure/commenting your code
- Documentation: written for developers/users. At GitHub, documentation can be included via a readme file or a [readthedocs](#) page.
- Collaborate with a version control system (git)
- [Example of software documentation](#)
- Think and plan how to actively collaborate!

Software citations

- Register your code in a community registry
- [Research software registries](#)
- Most generic is Zenodo (which has an [integration to GitHub](#)), where a persistent identifier is generated (doi)

#3
**REGISTER YOUR
CODE IN A
COMMUNITY
REGISTRY**

<https://fair-software.nl>

Software citations

- It is hard to cite a paper if you don't make it citable
- Citation helps software developers be recognized for their work, and make the software findable
- [CodeMeta](#) and the [Citation File Format](#) (CFF) are specifically designed to enable citation of software

Software citations

🕒 4 minute read

What is a CITATION.cff file?

`CITATION.cff` files are plain text files with human- and machine-readable citation information for software (and datasets). Code developers can include them in their repositories to let others know how to correctly cite their software.

This is an example of a simple `CITATION.cff` file:

```
cff-version: 1.2.0
message: "If you use this software, please cite it as below."
authors:
  - family-names: Druskat
    given-names: Stephan
    orcid: https://orcid.org/1234-5678-9101-1121
title: "My Research Software"
version: 2.0.4
identifiers:
  - type: doi
    value: 10.5281/zenodo.1234
date-released: 2021-08-11
```

The format of `CITATION.cff` files is the **Citation File Format (CFF)**.

ON THIS PAGE

WHAT IS A `CITATION.CFF` FILE?

WHY YOU SHOULD ADD A `CITATION.CFF` FILE TO YOUR REPOSITORY!

SUPPORTED BY GITHUB

SUPPORTED BY ZENODO

SUPPORTED BY ZOTERO

CREATE A `CITATION.CFF` FILE NOW!

TOOLS FOR WORKING WITH `CITATION.CFF` FILES

HAVE AN IDEA? FOUND A PROBLEM?

Software in publications

- Apart from providing a research software link or software citation to your research paper, some journals are designed to publish software specifically (separate from the methods)

Visibility/Platforms

How to find research software?

Database	Search terms	Search within	Items found	Included items found
Scopus	<i>"open source" AND "room acoustics" OR "room impulse response" AND "model*" OR "simulation" OR "prediction" OR "software"</i>	Article title, Abstracts, Keywords	31	9
the Lens*	<i>"open source" AND ("room acoustics" OR "room impulse response") AND "model*" OR "simulation" OR "prediction" OR "software"</i>	-	44	7
GitHub	<i>Room Acoustics</i>	-	84	9
	<i>Room Impulse Response</i>	-	110	
Paperswithcode**	<i>Room Acoustics</i>	-	40	19
	<i>Room Impulse Response</i>	-	37	
Scopus	<i>"room acoustics" OR "room impulse response" AND "model*" OR "simulation" OR "prediction" OR "software"</i>	Article title, Abstracts, Keywords	1957	NA

Visibility/Platforms

- How to find research software?
- Enlarge visibility of your software
- [Research Software Directory](#) (you can add your package yourself)
- [Papers with code](#) (your work might be picked up here)
- Appear in lists as [open source software room acoustics](#)

Software quality/reviewing

- [Checklists](#) help you write good quality software
 - Get your [Core infrastructures initiative](#) badge
 - [FAIR software checklist](#)

OpenSSF Best Practices Badge Program

[Get Your Badge Now!](#)

The [Open Source Security Foundation \(OpenSSF\)](#) Best Practices badge is a way for Free/Libre and Open Source Software (FLOSS) projects to show that they follow best practices. Projects can voluntarily self-

The logo for the OpenSSF Best Practices Badge Program. It features a blue shield with a yellow gradient background. Inside the shield is a blue trophy cup with the text "OpenSSF BEST PRACTICES" on it. A blue penguin head is positioned to the right of the trophy, appearing to look at it.

<https://www.bestpractices.dev/en>

Software quality/reviewing

- Is the software behind a paper accessible and does it produce the results of the paper?
- Badge systems by independent reviewers could help out here
 - [CodeCheck Certificate](#): certificate of executable computation
 - [ACM badges](#): more versatile reviewing system

Training

- [CodeRefinery](#) online courses
 - [Introduction to version control](#) (day 1-2): **Why we want to track versions and how to go back in time to a working version.** This lesson brings you from zero to using Git and GitHub for own projects.
 - [Collaborative distributed version control](#) (day 3): This lesson builds on "Introduction to version control" and we apply branching and learn about pull requests (merge requests), forks, and collaboration using Git and GitHub.
 - [Reproducible research](#) (day 4): **Preparing code to be usable by you and others in the future.** We focus here on 3 aspects of reproducible programs and computations: documenting dependencies, environments, and computational steps in a reproducible way. We touch on containers.
 - [Social coding and open software](#) (day 4): **What can you do to get credit for your code and to allow reuse.** We motivate and give an overview over software and data licensing and software citation best practices.
 - [How to document your research software](#) (day 5): Here we give an overview of the different ways how a code project can be documented: from small projects to larger projects. Markdown and Sphinx are central tools in this lesson.
 - [Jupyter notebooks](#) (day 5): **A tool to write and share executable notebooks and data visualization.** This lesson gives an overview of what Jupyter notebooks are, when they can be particularly useful, and shows best practices for reusable and reproducible notebooks.
 - [Automated testing](#) (day 6): **Preventing yourself and others from breaking your functioning code.** In this lesson we talk about motivation for testing, about test design, but also about some tools that are typically used for automated testing of software.
 - [Modular code development type-along](#) (day 6): **Making reusing parts of your code easier.** The focus of this lesson is how to partition and organize projects as they grow from one screen-full to larger and how to make code portions reusable across projects and across notebooks.

Training

- [Software carpentry](#) online courses
- [eScience center](#)
- [Software Sustainability Institute](#)

Course

Library Carpentry: FAIR Data and Software

This Library Carpentry workshop is still in the pre-alpha stage being designed and assembled. It cov...

View Course

Library Carpentry FAIR software

Course

Managing Academic Software Development

Developing academic software is a complex process. This workshop (which is in Beta version as a Soft...

View Course

Software development
Software Carpentry

Course

Software Carpentry Lessons

Software Carpentry workshops focus on three core software skills: Unix shell, version control with G...

View Course

The Carpentries Software Carpentry

<https://www.software.ac.uk/training/training-hub>

Further reading/useful links

- [Open science training handbook](#)
- [The Carpentries: teaching foundational coding and data science skills to researchers](#)
- [Five recommendations for fair software](#)
- [Comparison GitHub versus GitLab](#)
- [Citation File Format \(CFF\)](#)
- [Research Software Registries](#)
- [Choose a licence](#)
- [eScience Center \(Netherlands\)](#)
- [Handbook to reproducible, ethical and collaborative data science](#)
- [Software Sustainability Institute](#)

Unlocking the impact potential of research software

Maarten Hornikx, m.c.j.hornikx@tue.nl

